

Bodily Experience in Space and Design: The Case of a First Year Studio Project at ITU Department of Architecture

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Abstract

In this paper, one of the projects of the first year design studio at ITU Faculty of Architecture, entitled “body-space-function” is introduced in relation to the notion of “bodily experience”. In this studio, students have designed an object as an extension of the body which co-exists with its visual and functional integrity by applying the different ways of seeing and thinking, discovering patterns and relationships, not only stimulating intellectually but also satisfying emotionally and spiritually. Students were asked to design an object as the extension of body, contributing its functional entity with its portable and transformable character and to give a reasonable “name” in accordance with the theme. In order to support this experiential approach to design, the “Dance workshop” and “Jewelry workshop” which have contributed to students’ awareness of bodily experience in space can be considered as emotion-driven tools in design education. The aim of this paper is to examine the steps of the design process in a mutual interplay of emotion and thought, to illustrate the contribution of workshops to the development of creative thinking and to discuss the design products and personal experiences of students by using visual materials.

Keywords: body-space-function, design education, emotion-driven space, experiential approach, bodily experience

Design and experience

Today design knowledge can be considered as an interface between knower and known because of its changing and interactive character. Design is commonly considered as the ‘process of possibility’. Since the design knowledge has an ambiguity it cannot be transmitted; it can be discovered within a medium that carries a message through the interactive relations between the source of knowledge and the experiencing subject. These interactive relations are called reciprocal relations that explain the dialectics of thought and emotion which facilitates to uncover the hidden dimensions of design issues.

Since designers are considered as creators of ‘potential products’ for ‘potential users’, their role might be interpreted as those who create potential experiences. All design products give rise to abstract and concrete experiences for its users. Consequently design is always a

process which involves the consumer as well as the product. Identifying the fact that the design issue is not only consist of products but also experiences, the power of design might be controlled and directed to well-being phenomenon. Considering this phenomenon, the designer has to imagine and make projections / predictions for the tangible and intangible experiences of the user. Here the question comes along: for creating potential experiences, can experiencing personally, using the 'self' as a means of experience be a supportive method for this ambiguous creation process? In order to design for the 'other', design for the self might be a leading way to ease the difficulties of trying to be in someone else's shoes. In this respect, paying attention to oneself and essentially to the senses of the self, trying to experience various bodily senses, relations between senses enables a good foundation for the beginning of an experience design.

As Victor Papanek states "all people are designers, everything we do, almost all the time, is design, for design is basic to all human activity. The planning and patterning of any act towards a desired and predictable objective constitutes the design process. Design is the primary underlying matrix of life" (Papanek, 1970). Design education, therefore embodies a mission of shaping the spontaneity of everyday experience into a consciousness. To be aware of this spontaneous design experience will facilitate to understand the unity and complexity of the design issues. Another question might be put forward now. Could it be easier using oneself as the means of experience during the transition from spontaneous design to conscious design? Can we introduce consciousness in design education by using this self-designing practice? By discovering their bodily experiences they bring their emotions and thought together, and will be able to design with more awareness for the self before designing for the 'other'. This kind of exercise would require an exploration/discovery of oneself with an intensive self / bodily experience.

Victor Papanek draws his theses on his self-conception as a "human engineer" in his books 'Design for human scale' and 'Design for the Real World', and asks "why things you buy are expensive, badly designed, unsafe and usually don't work!" (design now.austria). He pursues a well tailored design for the human. This type of engineering aims at making human life more efficient and satisfying.

Wolfgang Welsch (1995)'s thesis also indicates that we are currently living through two changes: "the 'virtualization or de-realization of the real and of our understanding of reality',

and a 're-validation of non-electronic experiences of reality'. This point of view goes parallel to Papanek's human based design idea of the 70s. While the world of electronic media widely dominates our lives, such a return to real experiences justifies the importance of bodily experiences in design and design education because the body is in the very centre of our experience.

The role of emotion and bodily experience in design

Design is a cyclic process, a process of feeding our human desires with some products...the process of developing forms of interaction between the tangible world and people's intangible emotions (Arbak, 2000). During the last 30 years the focus of design studies as a rational science has moved from rationalism to pragmatism and phenomenological approaches exploring specific designerly skills and ways of doing design. The "pragmatic turn" meant an orientation towards design, towards doing, communication and participation, whereas the "corporeal turn" added a focus on our bodily experiences of artifacts in use (Ehn, 2004).

Critics also cite the body together with meanings and ideas. J. F. Lyotard asks: "Might 'idea' exist without a body?". This question-statement justifies the requirement of the thought for the body for its realization. Baudrillard also emphasizes the meaning of the body as such: "among other consumed things, there is an object nicer, more valuable, more unique than other objects, which even though sums up all others, is more loaded with side meanings than a car. This object is "the body". For Ann Glane, the body interprets other bodies' actions through senses and thus can perform actions on other bodies (Çalikoğlu, 2004).

Merleau-Ponty goes beyond the physiological and psychological researches and deals with the phenomenological description of the body and the spatiality associated with it. The change he put in the notion of body image implies a crucial shift from the body as object to the body as lived, as experienced. The way of structuring the environment is an experience which can not be reduced to a summation of sensory contents (Langer, 1989).

Merleau-Ponty's well known articulation of the "body-subject" was to identify the "origin of the object in the very centre of our experience". He concluded that this center was, quite simply, the body. One of his main arguments involves a critique of the idea of a sovereign

self that is seen as distinct from the body. The mind and body are one inseparable unity, which is the subject (University of Sydney, 2004). He draws that it is the body which encounters others and the world, not an abstracted mind which somehow inhabits that body. Therefore bodies are "lived experience". The body-subject's lived experience is necessarily of location because its language is that of gestures, movements and action (Langer, 1989).

Since bodily experience in space requires the unity of the emotion and thought, design proceeds in a reciprocal relationship between them. Design knowledge takes its roots from experiential and conceptual processes which are difficult to grasp with the conscious mind because of its abstract and intangible "facts". Experiential knowledge drives from the energizing power of the dialectics of emotion and thought. Students should therefore engage in an ongoing 'emotion-thought dialogue'; this is a primary significance reached through coexistence. In design education, hence it is not enough to train the outer senses and the intellect. Students must both improve their abilities to see outwardly and to develop their inner recognitions and perceptions in order to become more sensitive, open to emotions, understanding with greater empathy, concern and respect.

A design project for the 1st year architectural design studio:

"Body-Space-Function"

In 2003 – 2004 Academic year at ITU, the first year architectural students were faced with the design project called 'body-space-function', which is based on bodily experience and aims to develop the beginner of designers' concept of space. The students were asked to design an object as an extension of the body which co-exists with its visual and functional integrity by making use of the bodily experiences encountered through planned workshops.

The design assignment subject to this paper was one of the first studies of the design project 1 and basic design course at the Istanbul Technical University Architectural Faculty. 48 students formed the group. The course program consisted of 5 projects named as 'explorations', which are the treasure hunt, living building, topography-structure, thematical space design. The duration of these explorations were multi-layered and had transitions in between. All explorations were planned with enriching supports such as movies, workshops, seminars, lectures and discussions.

Exploration 3 was entitled as “body-space-function” which was a bodily experienced design. Duration of the assignment was 2.5 weeks, which was supported by two, day-long workshops (Table 1).

Weeks	1					2					3					4					5				
Course days	22.09.2003	24.09.2003	25.09.2003	26.09.2003	29.09.2003	01.10.2003	02.10.2003	03.10.2003	06.10.2003	08.10.2003	09.10.2003	10.10.2003	13.10.2003	15.10.2003	16.10.2003	17.10.2003	20.10.2003	22.10.2003	23.10.2003	24.10.2003	27.10.2003				
introduction																									
invisible cities																									
on studio																									
sketches																									
exploration 1											Treasure hunt														
discussion																									
exploration 2											Living building														
workshops																									
exploration 3											Body-space-function														

Table 1, The whole semester program of the course. The project and two workshops integrated to it are highlighted.

The aim of this exercise was to lead the student to explore the body usage, experience by measuring his/her own body dimensions. They have tried to discover the potentials of the body having idiosyncratic characteristics of the individual. In order to discover the other modes of expression and understanding, particularly affective and symbolic languages of various spatial characters, in first year design studio students were faced a project based on bodily experience.

The design project ‘body-space-function’ is a ‘new’ design object, which will bring these three concepts together, it will enable to consider these concepts as a whole as well as separately. It will bring a new dimension to the body’s known functional characteristics. This is going to be an extension design fulfilling the visual and functional accordance with the part of the body it is added on. This inevitably has to be an original design, an unknown discovery that will come out with the imagination, observation and logical thinking skills. Students are asked to identify their design with a specific title. In this design process, where ideas progress with metaphors, new perceptions and new relationships will guide this design. The discussion themes for the design would be; their functional contributions to the body, portable and transformable character, usage time/period, place/body, being personal ...

The questions to be answered throughout the process are;

- What is its existing reason?
- Which function/act will it facilitate?
- When will it be used?
- How will it be carried?

The students are encouraged to use a variety of materials in this design exercise including all kinds of waste and recycle materials (pizza boxes, cans, cola cans, etc.) as well as common modeling materials.

In order to enrich this design project, two supportive contexts/works were planned as the following one-day workshops, which would be realized simultaneously with the design work. These are;

- a workshop about the location of the body in space, the body as defining the limits of the space - **the Dance workshop**,
- A workshop for a design object derived from the body – **the Jewel workshop**.

These two workshops would contribute to our bodily experience ability, add new dimensions to functionality and broaden horizons for the entirety of the design idea for the existing and its designed extension.

Workshops that support the design project

Jewelry Workshop

Jewelry as an attachable/wearable object continues its development throughout history by constituting social identity. Due to the characteristic of the sociality, jewelry is considered as a very important data in social meaning analyses. Today jewelry design is one of the creative ways for the artists and ingenious people to explain them. Recently, all kinds of materials are used in jewelry and it gets value from its design, not only by its material.

The design task of “a personal object carried on the finger” is given as the workshop subject to the students who would be both the designer and the user during one-day workshop under the supervision of the jewelry designer Zeynep Erol. The contributions of the workshop to the project respectively are, the students’ comprehension of their own personal sizes, the definition/recognition and formability of materials (brass, wax, stones, sequins, strings,

polish...), injecting a clever remark to the object and creativity by the reflection of designer/user's mood instead of being only an adornment. They also have made numerous trials of their designed object on their bodies, so all day they had intensely bodily experiences (Figure 1). Therefore their design outcome has been one of a perfect fit to their bodies.

Figure 1, jewelry artist working with students at the workshop and the products.

Dance Workshop

“Dance transforms body into an object..” Paul Valéry

“Not body’s, but mind’s choreography is essential.” Dieter Rehberg (Günsur, 2002)

Dance is one of the basic arts which was subject to develop ideas on in every era. Some qualities which make it universal are being an important part of the ceremonies, an essence of life. From Homo- Sapiens to modern man, human being use dance as a language to explain its happiness, anxieties, and fears. Dance is such a special activity that establishes its own space-time dialectic with human body momentum.

The aim of the one-day workshop supervised by Aydın Teker (from the department of Modern Dance in Mimar Sinan University) was the comprehension of the space with the body. The supervisor is generally focused on body-space relations in her choreographies. In this respect, the workshop place Taşkılla Venus Hall, with its unique spatial qualities enables an adequate milieu for this activity.

Figure 2, Concepts defining the alignment of the body.

Figure 3, Dance workshop and positive-negative space created by the students.

At this experience, the supervisor introduced the students some concepts defining the alignment of the body through imagery. These are planes like the sagittal plane (see above), the transverse / horizontal plane and the lateral (frontal/coronal) plane which in effect define the body with the help of planes. Terms like the central axis, center of gravity can be considered as some existent axes of to the body (Figure 2).

The workshop can be summarized as the non-musical dance experience in Taşkıışla Venus Hall, definition of the body by the planes, creation of the solids/voids within the space by the body (Figure 3), a motion experience underlying the physical properties of the space, personal performances. Additionally, this workshop is such a significant reminiscence that participants will remember in all their design activities.

Being spectators at the modern choreographed “Carmina Burana” Ballet performed in Atatürk Cultural Center was a significant experience for some students who originally came from small Anatolian towns.

Outcomes of the design work

The following categories can be made in terms of design approaches when the design outcomes are examined. These categories are explained with their sample works.

The questions that were put forward at the beginning of the design problem for the definition of the project;

What is its existing reason?

Which function/act will it facilitate?

When will it be used?

How will it be carried?..

may help evaluating the final products. The table below (table 2) is an attempt to reconsider the projects by the light of these essential questions. The routes of these questions in the students' minds, which were enriched by the workshop supervisors' vision have led the students to design original unique and creative products. This creativity is achieved through the power of experience and close relationship with the body.

To increase the potential of a limb/organ....

By examining the structure of a limb/organ to increase its own potential

Project: *a lengthening arm*

Function:
to grab an object that is far away by using the arm's joint movement

Project: *walking support*

Function:
to delay fatigue by minimizing the load on the body when walking

To use the potential of a limb/organ...

To evaluate the original structure of a limb/organ.

Project: *kurbiş*

Function:
to rearrange the structure by using the logic of the palette or hand

Project: *new digit or finger*

Function:
a pen with an eraser
attached to a finger

To utilize the potential of the limb/organ with other functions...

By evaluating the potential of the limb/organ to use it for a different function

Project: *chewer*

Function:
to give the function
of chewing with massaging
of the head

Representations/Objects that bring the places of utilization into mobility

Representations/Objects attached to the body and used when necessary.

Project: *three-in-one*

Function:
by carrying on the body
things such as a light, pen, ruler used in
drawing, sketching, etc.,
to be used at an appropriate time

A new limb/organ attached to the body:

By examining the structure of the limb/organ to create a new organ to be attached to the body

Project: *a third hand*

Function:
by using the joints
creating a third hand
controlled by the present hand.

Representations replacing limbs/organs...

To create a new function that is included in the function of the limb/organ

Project: *headphones*

Function:
a telephone box that establishes
a connection that is put on
top of the head.

Representations/Objects carried by the body and combine two functions...
Representations/Objects that have alternative functions

Project: diabetic watch

Function:
for reminding the hours
to take medicine

To experiment with the potential of the limb/organ...

To use the potential of the limb/organ while in motion

Project: rhythm set

Function:
by making attachments of
the joints to create a sound system
that uses the motion of the body

To strengthen a product that is being used by supporting with the body...

To make more effective the products that we use in daily life by utilizing the potential of the body

Project: *hair -clean up*

Function:
to clean body hair
from places such as sinks
by using the circular motion
of the hand.

Project: *mr. muscle*

Function:
to strengthen the muscles
by using the motion of the arm

Representations/Objects that control the motion of the body

To control and make static motions of the body such as falling, flailing, etc.

Project: *ivy*

Function:
to control the motions of
the body that result from
the motions of the bus.

Project: *neck protection*

Function:
to prevent injury to the neck
that results from involuntary
motion during travel.

Table 2, Examined and categorized sample works

In the first project of the design education in which the bodily experience of design is emphasized, the contributions for students can be summarized as follows:

Giving the first project topic as a non- architectural structure motivated students being open-minded for further design problems. They will be able to think flexible and to transform their design knowledge into various design problems. They become aware of the contextual design issues and to deal with the difficulties of changing principles.

As an extension of the body, their own model of 1/1 scale object was important for both the usage of their own size in further designs and comprehension of the “human scale”.

Designing in a full scale helped students to be able to think in a different way – in a tension between the reality and virtuality/possibility. The act of conceiving with the body, in other words bodily experience, came out as a result of both movement directed by space and the functioning principles of the articulations.

Experimentation and discovery of the body were accelerated by one-day workshops. Jewelry workshop helped students to understand the relation between the body and object supporting both functional and visual continuity. During the dance workshop, students were motivated to perceive the potentials of the body by moving through the space creating positive and negative space. They became aware of the shifting balance of positive and negative space using their bodies in this workshop.

Different scales were used in bodily experienced workshops. Jewelry workshop has been realized to motivate students understanding the mutual relationship between the object and the subject. The designed object was considered as an extension of the finger-hand-body. The

dance workshop, which was held in Taşkışla having an idiosyncratic character, enhanced students to discover the shifting balance of the solid/body and the void/space.

Conclusion

The Design Project for the 1st Year Architectural Design Studio: “Body-Space-Function” proposes a method for an emotion-driven design. Determination of objectives in the beginning of the project is organized in accordance with the study process. The objectives are as follows: construction of an alternative function to the body, a cursive mechanism evaluation and recycling of scarp materials mobility and transformability. The student at this initial state of the education is considered to be mostly free from design prejudices and obsessions. Taken this fact into consideration, initially approaching design by relating to one’s own body is considered as a more adequate method. This actually is an experimental initial exercise for the design education, which will eventually proceed as a more architecture-oriented education.

Discovering the potentials of the body having idiosyncratic characteristics of the individual, creating a phenomenon based on the reality of bodily experience, contributing its functional entity with its portable and transformable character are the design problems that would be captured with intuition. Intuitive knowledge, which was the result of a reciprocal interplay between rational and emotional domains, has obtained through experience and increasingly dominated the design decisions. Obviously creativity requires self-motivation and it is natural being motivated towards things we relate a sense of excitement and joy. An exercise based on bodily experience and intuition is an exercise that the subject is familiar to the designer. In such a design project, allowing to be highly motivated, creativity is expected to be at its maximum. With this feature at hand, a bodily experience design project seems very satisfactory for the initial state of the design education.

As a result, it is also possible to discuss the problems of experiential design knowledge that provides an excellent opportunity for using emotions and transforming them into intuition. Bodily experience in space will give rise to the power of grasping or intuitively understanding the essence of spatial effects. Intuition helps students to develop the sensibility and self-motivation, which leads to creative, flexible, tolerant and liberal personality, who can face the complexity and ambiguity of design problems.

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